

The moderating role of perceived social support in the relationship between co-rumination and depressive symptoms

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Abstract

It is generally agreed that there are advantages as well as disadvantages to co-rumination, which is defined as excessively discussing problems with another person, particularly by rehashing them and dwelling on the unpleasant feelings associated with them. Co-rumination, perceived social support, and depressive symptoms may all be associated but the precise extent of that relationship remains unclear. This study aims to test the moderating role of perceived social support in the relationship between co-rumination and depressive symptoms among teaching personnel. Respondents were recruited from a private higher educational institution in Bacoor City, Cavite, Philippines. Out of 460 who were given the e-survey, a total of 135 (29%) responses were gathered. The 135 participants included 53 males (39.3%) and 82 females (60.7%). The mean age of the sample was 34.23 years ($SD = 12.15$ years). In terms of parental status, 62 (45.93%) have at least one (1) child while 73 (54.07%) are non-parents. The Multidimensional Scale of Perceived Social Support (MSPSS), the Co-Rumination Questionnaire (CRQ), and the Beck Depression Inventory-II (BDI-II) were among the validated tools used in the online survey. The results of Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) analysis revealed that there is significant positive relationship between co-rumination and depressive symptoms. Thus, when respondents' co-rumination increases, depressive symptoms also increase. Moreover, results found that perceived social support is a factor that moderate the relationship between the two variables.

Keywords: Co-rumination; depressive symptoms; perceived social support.

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Introduction

Maintaining open communication with one another and making the most of your time together are two methods to develop supportive and close partnerships. But, if we do not pay attention to what we share with our friends, it is possible that our interactions with them unknowingly increase our levels of worry and despair. Although while it feels good to have a significant other affirm our emotions, asking for it in an excessive way might be more detrimental than helpful. Co-rumination is a practice of talking about difficulties with friends while dwelling on unpleasant feelings, thinking too much about the reasons of a problem, and worrying about its repercussions, which raises the risk of depression and anxiety among teenagers and young adults (Stone et al., 2019).

Co-rumination is a subpar method of managing emotions that just serves to maintain detrimental consequences and raise cortisol levels in the body. This method does not emphasize problem-solving and does not encourage pro-active coping. Co-rumination serves to exacerbate rather than alleviate issues. According to Zhou et al. (2020), co-rumination can cause emotional distress as well as physical harm, but it also appears to be socially reinforced through increased friendship quality and emotional validation, masquerading as helpful social support.

Keshishian et al. (2016) suggest that talking to peers about the pandemic's unfavorable emotions, concerns, and potential impacts might exacerbate internalizing symptoms, particularly health anxiety. Preliminary research indicates that talking and texting at the same time is only associated with friendship quality, not worry. It is essential to fully understand the impact of co-rumination because it can significantly affect wellbeing and because the phenomena remains uncommon in this setting.

Despite knowing that co-rumination is related to perceptions of positive relationships, participants report fewer conflicts with others in their social circle. Those who co-ruminate also frequently report experiencing signs of internalization. As a result, co-ruminating inclinations can raise a person's risk of experiencing social problems, sadness, and anxiety symptoms. Since a component of co-ruminative rumination has been likened to depressed rumination, it may be connected to internalizing symptoms like depression (Rose, 2002). Co-rumination in the past is a predictor of future rumination, according to longitudinal research (Felton et al., 2019).

On the link between co-rumination and depression

Will (2021) says that teachers are almost twice as likely as other adults to feel stress at work on a regular basis and almost three times as likely to show signs of depression. These results show the cost of a school year that had little to do with the Covid-19 pandemic, and many teachers say it has made them think about leaving their jobs.

Even before the pandemic, teaching was a stressful job, but this school year has made the problem even worse. Among teaching staff, having good relationships with colleagues has become a major source of emotional support. Sharing personal information with a friend makes you feel closer to them and fills your need to belong, which is good for your emotional health. Co-rumination, on the other hand, is a way of talking about bad things with friends that has been shown to be bad for mental health.

Co-rumination is a very bad form of self-disclosure in which people talk about their problems and feelings to the exclusion of all other topics or activities (Rose, 2002). In line with Rose's theory, a growing body of evidence has shown that the amount of co-rumination teens and adults do is linked to their current symptoms of depression (Starr & Davila, 2009).

On perceived social support among teaching personnel

Li et al. (2022) conducted a study in which they discovered that in addition to the immediate implications of life satisfaction and coping style, teachers' social support also affects their mental health literacy through the chain mediation effect of these two factors. Social support does not, however, have a large direct impact on teachers' mental health literacy. This study reveals the inner workings of the link between social support and mental health literacy. It served as a reminder that while creating programs to assist teachers in learning more about mental health, we should consider more than just providing them with the social support they require to recover—we should also consider how they handle challenges and how content they are with their lives.

In the related literature, social support is described in different ways. Tasdan and Yalcin (2010) said that social support is the social and emotional help a person gets from their surroundings. Also, there is a strong connection between social support and work engagement and teacher effectiveness (Minghui et al., 2018).

On the link between social support and depression

A plenty of literature has been written about the link between social support and depression. Also, many studies show a link between social support and low depression (Ellonen et al., 2008; Dingfelder et al., 2010). Some studies have looked at the link between perceived social support and depression. One of these is the social causation model, which says that lack of social support leads to psychological anguish, and social support is an indicator of wellbeing (Kaniasty & Norris, 2008). This model explains the link between social support and stress and predicts that social support makes depression less likely (Zhen et al., 2018). Social support may help people with depression by making them feel better about themselves and making them think less negatively (Ren et al., 2018).

Conceptual Framework

According to the social support theory, social support is a stable resource that keeps people from getting depressed (Lakey, 2008). Psychological symptoms like depression, anxiety, and posttraumatic stress (PTS) symptoms, are less likely to happen if a person feels like they have social support.

This is a fact that has been proven over and over again. Thomas et al. (2022) found that a stress-buffering mechanism could protect against depressive symptoms in people who felt they had more social support. In the same study, it was found that low social support is linked to a wide range of mental health issues, such as non-specific psychological distress, post-traumatic stress disorder, eating disorders, low self-esteem, and clinical depression. Also, the stress-mobilizing hypothesis says that stress makes people more likely to look for social support (Singh & Dubey, 2015).

Figure 1. Conceptual framework on the role of perceived social support in the relationship between co-rumination and depressive symptoms of teaching personnel

Statement of the Problem

The primary goal of this study was to examine whether perceived social support moderates the relationship of co-rumination and depressive symptoms among teaching personnel in selected private institutions in Bacoor City, Cavite. The researcher hypothesized that the respondents' co-rumination is positively correlated with their depressive symptoms and that perceived social support moderates the relationship between the two variables at a significant level. Specifically, the researcher aims to answer the following research questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of the following:
 - a. co-rumination
 - b. perceived social support
 - c. depressive symptoms?
2. Is there a significant relationship between the respondents' co-rumination and depressive symptoms?
3. Does perceived social support moderate the relationship between the respondents' co-rumination and depressive symptoms?

Methodology

Respondents

The respondents who took part in the study were chosen by the researcher using a purposive sample technique. This methodology refers to a collection of non-probability sampling techniques where units are chosen because they possess study-relevant features.

Participants in this study are teaching personnel from St. Dominic College of Asia (SDCA), a private higher education institution in Bacoor City, Cavite, Philippines. Out of the 460 people who were given the e-survey, only 135 (29%) filled it out. 53 men (39.3%) and 82 women (60.7%) were among the 135 people who took part. The average age of the group was 34.23 years (standard deviation = 12.15 years).

In terms of whether or not they have children, 62 (45.93%) do and 73 (54.07%) do not. Table 1 shows more about the participants' ages, genders, and other characteristics.

Table 1. Socio-demographic characteristics of the sample (n = 135)

Demographic Variables	Male	Female	Total
Number	53 (39.3%)	82 (60.7%)	135 (100%)
Age (M ± SD)	33.55 ± 12.15	34.67 ± 12.21	34.23 ± 12.15
Socioeconomic Status			
Below 10,000 pesos	11 (8.15%)	18 (13.33%)	29 (21.48%)
10,000 pesos and below	19 (14.07%)	31 (22.96%)	50 (37.04%)
20,001 to 30,000 pesos	8 (5.93%)	16 (11.85%)	24 (17.78%)
30,001 to 40,000 pesos	6 (4.44%)	8 (5.93%)	14 (10.37%)
More than 40,000 pesos	9 (6.67%)	9 (6.67%)	18 (13.33%)
Parental Status			
Parents	21 (15.56%)	41 (30.37%)	62 (45.93%)
Non-parents	32 (23.70%)	41 (30.37%)	73 (54.07%)

The demographic characteristics are presented in Table 1. As illustrated, out of 135 respondents, 82 (60.7%) are females and 53 (39.3%) are males. In terms of socioeconomic status, 29 (21.48%) of the respondents earn a monthly income of below 10,000 pesos; 50 (37.04%) earn a monthly income of 10,001 to 20,000 pesos; 24 (17.78%) earn a monthly income of 20,001 to 30,000 pesos; 14 (10.37%) earn a monthly income of 30,001 to 40,000 pesos; and 18 (13.33%) earn a monthly income of more than 40,000 pesos. Moreover, majority of the respondents are non-parents which consist of 73 or 54.07% of the total sample size, while 62 or 45.93% are working parents.

Instruments

The Co-rumination Questionnaire (CRQ; Rose, 2002) is a 27-item self-report instrument that assesses the extent to which individuals co-ruminate with their closest friends or coworkers. Items were created to measure an extreme form of self-disclosure that only discusses negative events or difficulties. A 5-point scale from "Not at all true" (1) to "Really true" (5) is used for participants to rate the veracity of statements. The participants' total co-rumination score is calculated by averaging their ratings across all 27 items. Cronbach's Alpha (coefficient alpha) analysis of data from non-clinical samples (n = 35) revealed adequate internal consistency for the CRQ ($\alpha = .83$). Also, the CRQ had a moderate reliability coefficient ($r = .54$) in non-clinical samples (n = 35) with a two-week gap between tests.

Beck Depression Inventory-II (BDI-II) is a self-report questionnaire based on the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders, Fifth Edition (DSM-V) symptoms. This makes it possible to measure a person's level of depression. This inventory contains 21 sets of statements, each with four possible responses spanning from 0 to 3. This instrument, the Beck Depression Inventory-II has an excellent reliability coefficient of 0.92. Since most of its items are identical to the DSM-V criteria for depression, its content is valid.

The Multidimensional Scale of Perceived Social Support (MSPSS) consists of 12 items ranging from "not at all" (0) to "always" (3). It measures perceived social support from family, friends, and their significant other. With a Cronbach's alpha of 0.80, the MSPSS scale displayed good internal consistency, and it was reliable when used again.

Data Gathering Procedure

Before collecting data, the researcher sent a letter to the Research Development Office of the institution of interest to obtain permission to conduct the study. In the letter, the nature and purpose of the study as well as the extent of the respondents' participation were explained in detail. For data collection, a Google form containing the demographic profile and questionnaires was utilized. In the guidelines, it was also specified that respondents' participation in the study is entirely voluntary, and they may choose not to participate. The confidentiality and privacy of the respondents' information were also ensured.

The link to the online survey was distributed to the respondents' Facebook Messenger Groups with the aid of their respective supervisors. The data collection period lasted two (2) weeks, during which time 135 (29.35%) of 460 faculty members from a private educational institution in Bacoor City, Cavite, Philippines responded to the survey.

Results

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents?

Table 2. Demographic profile of the respondents in terms of co-rumination (n = 135)

Demographic Variables		Low		Average		High		Total	
		f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
Gender	Male	3	2.22	24	17.78	26	19.26	53	39.26
	Female	1	0.74	37	27.41	44	32.59	82	60.74
	Total	4	2.96	61	45.19	70	51.85	135	100.00
Age (years)	18-24	0	0.00	12	8.89	21	15.56	33	24.44
	25-34	1	0.74	25	18.52	26	19.26	52	38.52
	35+	3	2.22	24	17.78	23	17.04	50	37.04
	Total	4	2.96	61	45.19	70	51.85	135	100.00
Monthly Salary	10,000 pesos and below	1	0.74	13	9.63	15	11.11	29	21.48
	10,001 to 20,000 pesos	2	1.48	19	14.07	29	21.48	50	37.04
	20,001 to 30,000 pesos	0	0.00	16	11.85	8	5.93	24	17.78
	30,001 to 40,000 pesos	1	0.74	4	2.96	9	6.67	14	10.37
	More than 40,000 pesos	0	0.00	9	6.67	9	6.67	18	13.33
	Total	4	2.96	61	45.19	70	51.85	135	100.00
Parental Status	Parents	3	2.22	29	21.48	30	22.22	62	45.93
	Non-parents	1	0.74	32	23.70	40	29.63	73	54.07
	Total	4	2.96	61	45.19	70	51.85	135	100.00

Table 2 illustrates the frequency distribution of the respondents' demographic profile according to their co-rumination as measured the Co-Rumination Questionnaire (CRQ). In summary, majority or 51.85% (f = 70) of the respondents scored high, 45.19% (f = 61) scored average, and only 2.96% (f = 4) scored low in co-rumination.

Of those who scored high, majority or 60.74% (f = 82) are females while only 39.26% (f = 53) are males. Those aged 25-34 reported the highest frequency of high co-rumination scorers at 19.26% (f = 26) compared to 15.56% (f = 21) in 18-24-year-olds, and 17.04% (f = 23) in those who were 35 years or older.

In terms of socioeconomic status, those who earn an average monthly income of 10,001 to 20,000 pesos represents the greatest number of high co-rumination scorers at 21.28% (f = 29), followed by those who earn 10,000 pesos and below at 11.11% (f = 15).

Moreover, respondents with a monthly income of 30,001 to 40,000 pesos as well as those who earn more than 40,000 pesos, each represent only 6.67% (f = 9) of the total number of high co-rumination scorers, while only 5.93% (f = 8) have a monthly income of 20,001 to 30,000 pesos. In terms of parental status, most non-parents scored high in co-rumination at 29.63% (f = 40) compared to only 22.22% (f = 30) of respondents who already have at least one (1) child.

Table 3. Demographic profile of the respondents in terms of perceived social support (n = 135)

Demographic Variables		Low		Moderate		High		Total	
		f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
Gender	Male	7	5.19	18	13.33	28	20.74	53	39.26
	Female	3	2.22	22	16.30	57	42.22	82	60.74
	Total	10	7.41	40	29.63	85	62.96	135	100.00
Age (years)	18-24	4	2.96	17	12.59	12	8.89	33	24.44
	25-34	3	2.22	13	9.63	36	26.67	52	38.52
	35+	3	2.22	10	7.41	37	27.41	50	37.04
	Total	10	7.41	40	29.63	85	62.96	135	100.00
Monthly Salary	10,000 pesos and below	4	2.96	10	7.41	15	11.11	29	21.48
	10,001 to 20,000 pesos	3	2.22	16	11.85	31	22.96	50	37.04
	20,001 to 30,000 pesos	0	0.00	9	6.67	15	11.11	24	17.78
	30,001 to 40,000 pesos	1	0.74	1	0.74	12	8.89	14	10.37
	More than 40,000 pesos	2	1.48	4	2.96	12	8.89	18	13.33
Total	10	7.41	40	29.63	85	62.96	135	100.00	
Parental Status	Parents	3	2.22	12	8.89	47	34.81	62	45.93
	Non-parents	7	5.19	28	20.74	38	28.15	73	54.07
	Total	10	7.41	40	29.63	85	62.96	135	100.00

Table 3 illustrates the frequency distribution of the respondents' demographic profile according to their perceived social support according to the Multidimensional Scale of Perceived Social Support (MSPSS). In summary, majority or 62.96% (f = 85) of the respondents scored high, 29.63% (f = 40) scored average, and only 7.41% (f = 10) scored low in perceived social support.

Most of those who scored high are female with 42.22% (f = 57) while only 20.74% (f = 28) are male. Those who are 35 years or older reported the highest frequency of high co-rumination scorer at 27.41% (f = 37) compared to 26.67% (f = 36) in 25-34-year-olds, and 8.89% (f = 12) in those between the age of 18-24 years old.

In terms of socioeconomic status, those who earn an average monthly income of 10,001 to 20,000 pesos represents the greatest number of high co-rumination scorers at 22.96% (f = 31), followed by those who earn 10,000 pesos and below and 20,001 to 30,000 pesos, each have a share of 11.11% (f = 15) of the total number of high scorer. Similarly, respondents with a monthly income of 30,001 to 40,000 pesos as well as those who earn more than 40,000 pesos, each represent only 8.89% (f = 12) of the total number of high scorers in perceived social support. In terms of parental status, most respondents with at least one (1) child scored high in perceived social support at 34.81% (f = 47) compared to only 28.15% (f = 38) who are non-parents.

Table 4. Demographic profile of the respondents in terms of depressive symptoms (n = 135)

Demographic Variables		Minimal		Mild		Moderate		Severe		Total	
		f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
Gender	Male	26	19.26	7	5.19	13	9.63	7	5.19	53	39.26
	Female	44	32.59	12	8.89	13	9.63	13	9.63	82	60.74
	Total	70	51.85	19	14.07	26	19.26	20	14.81	135	100.00
Age (years)	18-24	5	3.70	4	2.96	12	8.89	12	8.89	33	24.44
	25-34	27	20.00	10	7.41	9	6.67	6	4.44	52	38.52
	35+	38	28.15	5	3.70	5	3.70	2	1.48	50	37.04
	Total	70	51.85	19	14.07	26	19.26	20	14.81	135	100.00
Monthly Salary	10,000 pesos and below	10	7.41	2	1.48	10	7.41	7	5.19	29	21.48
	10,001 to 20,000 pesos	21	15.56	9	6.67	9	6.67	11	8.15	50	37.04
	20,001 to 30,000 pesos	16	11.85	5	3.70	3	2.22	0	0.00	24	17.78
	30,001 to 40,000 pesos	12	8.89	0	0.00	1	0.74	1	0.74	14	10.37
	More than 40,000 pesos	11	8.15	3	2.22	3	2.22	1	0.74	18	13.33
Total	70	51.85	19	14.07	26	19.26	20	14.81	135	100.00	
Parental Status	Parents	45	33.33	8	5.93	6	4.44	3	2.22	62	45.93
	Non-parents	25	18.52	11	8.15	20	14.81	17	12.59	73	54.07
	Total	70	51.85	19	14.07	26	19.26	20	14.81	135	100.00

Table 3 illustrates the frequency distribution of the respondents' demographic profile according to their depressive symptoms as measured by Beck Depression Inventory-II (BDI-II). In summary, out of 135 respondents, majority or 51.85% (f = 70) of the respondents have minimal depressive symptoms, 14.07% (f = 19) are mild, 19.26% (f = 26) are moderate, while only 14.81% (f = 20) are severe.

In terms of gender, 9.63% (f = 13) of females reported to have severe depressive symptoms while 5.19% (f = 7) are male. Those who are 18-24 years old reported the highest frequency of severe depressive symptoms at 8.89% (f = 12) compared to 4.44% (f = 6) in 25-34-year-olds, and only 1.48% (f = 2) in those who were 35 years or older.

In terms of socioeconomic status, those who earn an average monthly income of 10,001 to 20,000 pesos represents the greatest number of respondents who reported severe depressive symptoms with 8.15% (f = 11), followed by 5.19% (f = 7) of respondents who earn 10,000 pesos and below. Of the 20 respondents who reported severe depressive symptoms, 17 are non-parents while only three (3) have at least one (1) child which covers 12.59% and 2.22% of the total sample, respectively.

2. Is there a significant relationship between the respondents' co-rumination and depressive symptoms?

Table 5. Relationship Between Co-Rumination and Depressive Symptoms

Variables	Path Coefficients	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Co-Rumination → Depressive Symptoms	0.189	0.012	Reject H ₀	Significant

Table 5 shows that the relationship between co-rumination and depressive symptoms have B = 0.189 and p = 0.012. Since p-value is less than the significance level of 0.05, the researcher rejects the null hypothesis and concludes that there is a significant relationship between co-rumination and depressive symptoms. Thus, as co-rumination increases, the level of depressive symptoms of the respondents also increases.

3. Does perceived social support significantly moderate the relationship between the respondents' co-rumination and depressive symptoms?

Table 6. Moderation Effect of Perceived Social Support on the Relationship between Co-Rumination and Depressive Symptoms

Variables	Path Coefficients	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Co-Rumination → Perceived Social Support → Depressive Symptoms	0.155	0.032	Reject H ₀	Significant

Table 6 shows that the moderation effect of perceived social support on the relationship between co-rumination and depressive symptoms has B = 0.155 and p = 0.032. Since p-value is less than the significance level of 0.05, the researcher rejects the null hypothesis and concludes that perceived social support significantly moderates the relationship between co-rumination and depressive symptoms. Thus, as perceived social support of the respondents increases the relationship between co-rumination and depressive symptoms also increases.

Discussion

The primary purpose of this study was to determine if the experience of perceived social support moderates the relationship between co-rumination and depressive symptoms among teaching professionals working in the selected research location. The researcher assumed that respondents' co-rumination would have a positive correlation with their depressive symptoms, and that their perceived levels of social support would substantially attenuate this relationship.

In this particular study, 135 members of the teaching staff from a private higher educational institution in Bacoor City, which is located in the province of Cavite in the Philippines, took part. The sample has 82 females making up 60.7% of the total, with 53 males making up 39.3% of the total. The sample had a standard deviation of 12.15 years, with a mean age of 34.23 years.

On co-rumination and depressive symptoms

Despite the fact that there is a strong correlation between co-rumination and the presence of depressive symptoms (Bastin et al., 2021), there has been little research conducted on the subject's prevalence in adults, particularly among those who are employed in educational settings.

Structural Equation Modeling or SEM analysis is a method of multivariate statistical analysis that is utilized to examine the causal relationships between latent constructs and measurable variables. This method was used by the researcher to investigate the relationship between co-rumination and depressive symptoms. The findings showed that there is a substantial association between ruminating on negative thoughts and experiencing symptoms of depression. So, as respondents' levels of co-rumination increase, their levels of depressed symptoms also increase.

Figure 2. Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) Model

Hankin et al. (2010) discovered that regardless of gender, co-rumination predicted future increases in depressive symptoms. Positive correlations were found between co-rumination and depressive symptoms and positive aspects of friendship, but co-rumination did not predict longitudinal changes in depressive symptoms. In addition, when controlling for depressive symptoms, co-rumination was negatively associated with social anxiety (Starr & Davila, 2009).

On perceived social support as moderator between co-rumination and depressive symptoms

Further investigation using SEM found that a significant moderating effect of perceived social support on the link between co-rumination and depressive symptoms was present. It has been discovered that adults' levels of perceived social support and connectivity are stronger predictors of decreased depression than gender, levels of self-esteem, and the quality of sleep they get (Armstrong & Oomen-Early, 2009). There is a constant link between perceived social support and well-being. This is likely due to the fact that positive experiences can be provided by perceived high levels of support, love, and caring (Siedlecki et al., 2014). According to the findings of a review, a high level of perceived social support is associated with better outcomes for both physical and mental health (Pietromonaco et al., 2013).

In summary, this study suggests that while co-rumination give rise to potential depressive symptoms, social support from friends, family members and others who are available to provide material, psychological and overall support during times of need can make a great difference.

Recommendations

The current results could have a few important effects. First, as was mentioned above, the current findings add to a growing body of research that shows how co-rumination makes teachers more likely to have depressive symptoms. So, school administrators might want to think about how the institution can get support from the academic community. In short, more research needs to be done to find out if co-rumination can be used to predict the onset of diagnosable depressive disorders in the future.

After establishing the significance of perceived social support in the relationship between co-rumination and depression, the results of this study may be beneficial and may have great significance to the following:

Educational institutions. Since teaching personnel are often juggling work, school, and family responsibilities, this study would make them aware of the much-needed support for them by psychosocial support programs. In this way, they will be able to have more quality time for their family, which in turn, could also be helpful in taking care of their mental health.

Government and state policy makers. This study can be used as a reference for crafting legislation that will help teaching personnel who are disproportionately single and from low-income backgrounds, especially amid the current period of high inflation. This study can push for more affordable basic services and access to support that would indirectly reduce the teachers' affordability gap.

Psychologists, counselors, and therapists. This will help mental health professionals to integrate the results of the study in educating teaching personnel to cope with life challenges and embrace a positive perspective, so they can better perform their duties and responsibilities and build goals with their families. It could also be a means of identifying a new approach or enhancing a program to them maintain work-life balance.

Future researchers. This study can be a springboard to constructing similar research in a new context, location and/or culture. Furthermore, this study can be re-designed and/or expanded to benefit teaching personnel using another framework. Future studies can address the professional, spiritual, social, and other aspects that were not discussed thoroughly in this study.

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